

EVALUATION OF LIPID METABOLISM INDICATORS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PANCREATITIS COMBINED WITH HYPOTHYROIDISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878686>

Abstract

In our research, we evaluated the lipid profile of the blood plasma (total cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoproteins, high-density lipoproteins) and the peculiarities of the dynamics of their changes in patients with chronic pancreatitis combined with hypothyroidism. The study of the comorbidity of these pathologies is a rather promising area of clinical gastroenterology and endocrinology. The study revealed the most pronounced signs of dyslipidemia in the group of patients with chronic pancreatitis combined with hypothyroidism. This confirms the close connection of these pathologies and requires further treatment correction. The results indicate the need for a more comprehensive study of the course and interaction of these diseases in order to avoid complications of these diseases in the future.

Keywords: chronic pancreatitis, hypothyroidism, total cholesterol, high-density lipoproteins, triglycerides, low-density lipoproteins.

Introduction Despite numerous studies, diseases of the pancreas, as a rule, are difficult to diagnose and treat. Nowadays, the mortality rate from acute pancreatitis remains high, the diagnosis of chronic pancreatitis in the early stages is a special test for the doctor, its treatment is very often unsuccessful [1]. After all, for many years the pancreas has remained a mysterious and not understood organ for doctors of various specialties: therapists, gastroenterologists, surgeons, oncologists, geneticists, etc. [2].

According to existing modern data, the function of the pancreas is under the influence of a whole series of hormones, and thyroid hormones occupy a special, regulatory place in this series. Thyroid hormones have a multifaceted effect on the body, affecting all organ systems and metabolism as a whole [3]. Deficiency of thyroid hormones leads to disorders on the part of organs and systems - cardiovascular, respiratory, digestive organs, etc. The condition of pancreas in hypothyroidism remains the least studied in gastroenterology, although B.L. Baker and E.S. Pliske in 1957 pointed out that thyroid gland atrophy is observed when the thyroid gland is removed, and the use of thyroid hormones leads to the restoration of its mass and structure.

Pancreas is a fairly active and powerful regulator of many biological reactions in the body, therefore any pathological and even functional changes in it always lead to varying degrees of severity of metabolic disorders. Changes in lipid metabolism, regardless of the underlying disease, are quite often associated with the so-called lipid triad: an increase in the level of triglycerides (TG), atherogenic low-density lipoproteins (LDL), and a decrease in high-density lipoproteins (HDL). This triad lies at the basis of the pathogenesis of many diseases, as well as oxidative stress in general. [4]

Among the most frequent complications of hypothyroidism are also dyslipidemias, which are observed in most patients and lead to an increased risk of early development of atherosclerosis. Mechanisms of development of dyslipidemia in chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism are considered to be a number of biochemical changes: violation of the structure of total cholesterol (C); a decrease in the activity of the cholesterol ether transport protein and hepatic lipase, which provide approximately 30% of the reverse transport of cholesterol; violation of the structure of high-density lipoproteins (HDL), which leads to a violation of the reverse transport of cholesterol; a decrease in the number and sensitivity of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) receptors in the liver, which cause a decrease in the hepatic excretion of cholesterol and, subsequently, an increase in the levels of LDL and very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL); as well as impaired renal glomerular function (decreased glomerular filtration rate) and slowing of LDL clearance.

The aim of the study was to study changes in blood lipid spectrum indicators in patients with chronic pancreatitis combined with hypothyroidism.

Materials and methods.

To achieve the goal, 103 patients were examined using modern biochemical and instrumental research methods: 43 patients with chronic pancreatitis - group 1, 45 patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism - group 2, 15 patients were practically healthy individuals, included in group 3;

Lipid metabolism was determined using a biochemical selective automated analyzer "KONELAB 20i". Biochemical study of lipids included determining concentrations of cholesterol, TG, LDL, and HDL.

Research results

Dyslipidemia was observed in the patients of the 1st group, but they were more pronounced in the patients of the 2nd group (with combined pathology), which was the highest among all the compared groups: indicators of total cholesterol increased 1.81 times

($p < 0.05$), LDL cholesterol increased by 87.4% ($p < 0.05$) and TG by 2 times ($p < 0.05$) and HDL cholesterol decreased by 24.77% ($p < 0.05$) compared to practically healthy individuals.

Indicators of lipid metabolism in patients with chronic pancreatitis combined with hypothyroidism

Indexes	Patients with chronic pancreatitis (№1) (n=43)	Patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism (№2) n=45	Practically healthy, persons (№3) n=15
Total cholesterol (mmol/l)	5,3±0,17	6,39±0,09	3,54±0,17
Triglycerides (mmol/l)	167±0,18	259±0,23	129,33±0,49
Low-density lipoproteins (mmol/l)	2,55±0,46	3,41±0,63	1,82±0,27
High-density lipoproteins (mmol/l)	1,35±0,88	1,13±0,15	1,41±0,07

Conclusion. A significant difference in the indicators of cholesterol, LDL, and TG was noted in patients of the 2nd group compared to individuals of the 1st and 3rd groups. Thus, the most pronounced signs of dyslipidemia were found in patients with chronic pancreatitis combined with hypothyroidism, which confirms the close pathogenetic connection between such nosologies, a marker of thyroid insufficiency (increased TSH level, decreased T3 and T4 indicators), manifestations of dyslipidemia and damage to the pancreas. The study of the comorbidity of these nosologies is a rather promising area of clinical gastroenterology and endocrinology. The results prove the need for a more detailed study of the course and interaction of these diseases in order to avoid complications of these diseases.

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